

OBSERVING AVERSIVE BIAS IN COURT CASES DEALING WITH DEFENDANTS
SUFFERING FROM MENTAL ILLNESS

By

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Faculty Mentor Approval:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Russ Espinoza". The signature is fluid and cursive, with the first name "Russ" being more prominent and the last name "Espinoza" following in a similar style.

Professor/Dr. Russ Espinoza, Department of Psychology

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Thesis Proposal

Subject or Topic

The topic that I am interested in researching is how potential jurors perceive males with schizophrenia who have committed a crime (murder). My research questions are do jurors show more empathy/leniency towards defendant with schizophrenia compared to those with depression or no mental illness and how does the severity of a defendant's mental illness impact juror perceptions? I predict that jurors will show more leniency in criminal sentencing recommendations to defendants with schizophrenia compared to defendants with depression and defendants without a mental illness. The topic would be covered under abnormal and forensic psychology.

Importance of the study

The importance of the study is to view whether mitigating factors (such as mental illness) play a part in jury verdicts. If they do hold significant value, should certain mental illnesses, such as schizophrenia, be taken more seriously than one with a higher level of symptom management? It is to view potential factors of aversive bias in a legal standpoint regarding mental illness. It is also significant to show the effects of schizophrenia and how one suffering with schizophrenia does not view or make judgements of the world the same as one who is mentally stable. I am hoping to contribute more information about schizophrenia to the public to allow them to see that those suffering with this mental illness should not be individuals to be fearful of. This study is a chance to give the audience an insight on schizophrenia to hopefully begin eliminating stigma and bring awareness about mental illness in a legal standpoint and to take the time to learn all the different levels and aspects that go with mental illness.

Definitions

- Schizophrenia: a mental illness in which an individual perceives reality abnormally
 - Symptoms: delusions, hallucinations, disorganized thinking and speech, abnormal motor behavior or the lack of being able to function in a normal way, extreme mood changes, may be suicidal
- Stigma: a mark of dishonor or disgrace in regards to a characteristic of an individual or a group of people
- Insanity plea: when the defendant is found guilty and admits to the act committed but declares a lack of accountability due to a mental illness
- Jury decision (verdict): decision made after taking the case into consideration
- Aversive/implicit bias: attitudes or, in this case stereotypes, that may affect one's understanding, actions, and decisions unconsciously

Approach to your topic

For my study, I will begin with speaking forth about schizophrenia as well as symptoms, causes, and ending off with court cases that deal with male schizophrenics being put on trial. The introduction will allow readers to view similar instances and cases where males with schizophrenia are being charged for a crime that they believe they did not do or that they believe they did no wrong in doing it. I will state my hypothesis; the more significant the mental illness is, the more likely jurors will show leniency towards sentencing. I am drawing my theories from aversive bias and pre-judgement in jurors viewing a defendant with a mental illness.

The major problem I am investigating is if jurors fixate on the extra-legal factors such as schizophrenia rather than the actual crime the individual has committed; do the jurors already have a made up mindset that the individual should be put in jail due to them being a “danger” to society? The literature that I am building upon are articles and psychology journals regarding jury decision-makings, studies on schizophrenia, studies on autism, and studies on anxiety. With this study, I am hoping to add more to literature studies as I am seeking to answer the question on whether aversive/implicit bias play a role in the jury’s decision when perceiving an individual who is schizophrenic.

Data and Methodology

As of now, I understand that it will be very difficult in the stage that I am in to interview those suffering with schizophrenia that have committed a criminal act; therefore, the best approach I believe in collecting data is through Qualtrics. I will first start reading through secondary data such as previous court cases and literature that deal with schizophrenia itself or mental illnesses in the court system. With the guidance of Dr. Espinoza, we have come up with a 1 x 1 x 3 case study. The first 1 is the race of the defendant (white), the second 1 is the race of the victims (white), and the 3 is the mental state of each dependent (schizophrenia, depressed, and no mental illness). Participants will be presented with three mock court documents detailing a murder of three victims committed by a white defendant. They will realize that each mock document details the same murder, but the defendant’s mental illness will be varied. After reading each case, participants will then be asked to submit a sentence for each of the defendant and their culpability of the crime. A questionnaire will then appear to the participants asking about how they perceived each of the defendants by likeability of each defendant, culpability, and trustworthiness. The last set of questions will be the juror background information.

The next portion of the thesis will be the method. This part of the thesis will include descriptions of the design, participants, materials and procedure, and summary of the case. Next, would be the analysis of the case study which would lead to the statistics portion that carries on to the results. In the results, I will further analyze the questions that participants answered such as the likeability of each defendant, culpability, trustworthiness, and the sentencing each received.

After the results, there will be a discussion portion of the overall reason why the case was conducted. It will again summarize the findings, talk about schizophrenia in a legal standpoint, speak about limitations encountered during the process of the study, and what can be further done to have more concrete evidence and data. This will lead to the conclusion where I will speak about the significant implications that the case will bring.

Format Requirements

The APA format is appropriate for my study.

Chapter 1:

Introduction, Thesis Statement, and Argument Structure

Introduction

In approximate forty-four out of fifty states, a jail and or prison is stated to hold more mentally ill individuals compared to the largest state psychiatric hospital. That is an outstanding number of individuals that are not being allowed the treatments needed to cope with the suffering of a mental illness. The way the criminal justice system works in the United States is that a group of qualified individuals is presented as the jury and helps the judge decide whether they seem the defendant guilty or not guilty of the crime at hand; this is called a jury verdict. The Sixth Amendment of the United States Constitution, the Right to Trial by Jury, was to ensure the prevention of tyranny as well as allow a democratic system in the criminal justice system. Nonetheless, having forty-four states with jails and or prisons holding more mentally ill individuals than state psychiatric hospitals portrays that not all defendants are given equal justice and consideration for their mental illness. This demonstrates aversive bias towards defendants that are mentally ill, a problem for both the criminal justice system as well as those not given the medication and help that they need.

Aversive bias attitudes or, in this case, stereotypes, may affect one's understanding, actions, and decisions unconsciously. Unfortunately, aversive bias is quite common, yet complicated to detect due to people not realizing what they are doing wrong. According to John Dovidio, only a small portion of Americans still show explicit racism, yet most Americans hold stereotypical views implicitly. In any case, aversive bias is unacceptable, but aversive bias towards someone suffering from a mental illness can be life-threatening. There could be many possibilities in which jury members do not take into consideration mental illness as a prime factor. Reasons such as religion, lack of understanding of mental illness, past trauma, or experiences regarding mental illness, and or culture and beliefs. As stated before, jurors are allowed to give their verdict about the defendant, yet not all the factors are taken into consideration; factors such as mental illness. Due to this, many defendants are not given the psychiatric help they need before entering jail or prison for their crime.

Literature that will be applied in a later chapter allows people to observe cases where defendants with certain mental illnesses are not taken into consideration and are then prohibited from their right to treatment. On the other hand, there are other forms of academic literature that state that the mental illness of the defendant should only be taken into consideration during trial only if the mental illness is severe. That brings up the question, what mental illness is considered severe over another? I will be taking the opposing side of this argument, by stating that all

mental illnesses should be considered no matter the severity of the condition of the defendant, since the mental illness, at any given time, can be life-threatening to the individual.

Statement of the Problem

There is an ongoing need to understand the problem of aversive bias towards defendants who are suffering from a mental illness in the United States. According to the United States Department of Justice, there is the continued growth of mental illness throughout the criminal justice system. It can be assumed that individuals who are more severely mentally ill are incarcerated rather than hospitalized. The problem here is not that defendants with mental illnesses should not be allowed in jails or prisons, but that the jury may not take the mental illness into consideration when it comes to sentencing, leaving the defendant at risk of having no treatment to help them with their mental disorder. A study conducted in 2009 by the Treatment Advocacy Center, conducted a set of inmate interviews and found that 16.7% of inmates were suffering from a serious mental illness such as schizophrenia, depression, or other psychotic disorders. The percentage may not be of a high number, but that would be due to 31% of the inmates refusing to participate; one can infer that in that 31% of inmates, there were individuals suffering from some type of mental illness. As more defendants suffering from a mental illness are admitted to a jail or prison rather than a psychiatric hospital, studies can continue to inform clinical and forensic professionals about the lack of treatment and considerations given to the mental state of defendants during their time of sentencing.

Due to the absence of research comparing multiple mentally ill defendants who committed the same crime and sentence, the literature addresses this problem. In the justice system, most research focuses on one case of mental disorder, but it is important to discuss how and what makes one mental illness more serious and worth remembering during the trial compared to another. When dealing with a more violent offense, there are few studies that consider the seriousness of the defendant's mental disorder. Just one, written by Annik Mossiere and Evelyn M. Maeder, talks of contrasting schizophrenia with other illnesses in a murder case, out of all the papers I have read. The literature that I have studied points to a legal deficit in the field of research on schizophrenia relative to other mental illnesses.

Additional research could add to the current practice by stating a more recent number of inmates in jails or prisons that are not receiving the adequate treatment a psychiatric hospital would give these individuals. At the same time, researchers would also be able to conduct a study that compares the severity of each mental illness compared to others through the variables of defendants suffering through these mental illnesses and view if the jurors consider their mental state during the jury verdict. The problem that this study address is the need to understand and take into consideration the mental state of mentally ill defendants as well as observe whether aversive bias towards these defendants plays a role in jury verdicts.

Purpose Statement

The objective of the study is to address whether mitigating factors, such as mental illness, should play a role in jury verdicts using a quantitative approach. Utilizing a quantitative approach, participants will answer four forms, (the juror verdict and sentence form, the juror opinion form, the personal evaluation of the defendant form, and the juror memory form) for each of the three mock-court cases. Aversive bias will be observed through analyzing the answers given by each participant playing the role of an individual juror. This study compares a defendant with schizophrenia to a defendant with depression as well as to a defendant with no mental illness at all to view if the severity of the mental illness is taken into consideration during jury verdicts. At the same time, this study also compares a defendant with a mental illness to a defendant without a mental illness. The overall goal is to analyze if mental illness holds a significant part in jury sentencing, and if so, compare the diverse types of mental illnesses to observe whether one has more of an impact on the sentencing than the other.

Research Questions

In order to accomplish these objectives, I have posed the following research questions and hypotheses that will guide this quantitative research study.

1. Do jurors show more empathy towards defendants with a mental illness?
2. Do jurors show more leniency in criminal sentencing towards a defendant with schizophrenia compared to a defendant with depression or no mental illness?
3. Do jurors show more leniency towards a defendant with depression compared to a defendant with no mental illness?
4. How does the severity of a defendant's mental illness impact juror perceptions?

This study builds on previous research regarding court cases and jury verdicts that have examined whether people take into consideration the mental state of a defendant. First, participants will complete a juror verdict and sentence form for each defendant of the study. Previous research has not combined multiple defendants with different mental disorders in one study and asked participants to identify the defendant with the mental illness. This study will have three defendants, and each has a different state of mind: one with schizophrenia, one with depression, and one without a mental illness. Secondly, I will ask participants to give their opinions on each defendant through a juror opinion form. Third, participants will answer a personal evaluation form on each defendant. Lastly, I will examine if participants remembered the mental illness of the court case that they had previously read a juror memory form.

My hypotheses are as follows:

- Jurors will show more leniency towards defendants with mental illness.
- Defendants with schizophrenia will have a more lenient sentencing compared to a defendant with depression or no mental illness.
- Defendants with depression will have a more lenient sentence compared to a defendant with no mental illness.
- The severity of a defendant's mental illness will substantially impact juror perceptions.

Definitions of Key Terms

The following list provides the terms and their definitions necessary to aid in understanding the jargon within the literature.

- Aversive/implicit bias: attitudes or, in this case stereotypes, that may affect one's understanding, actions, and decisions unconsciously.
- Depression: a mood disorder that causes one to feel long periods of sadness as well as loss of interest for daily activities.
- Insanity plea: when the defendant is found guilty and admits to the act committed but declares a lack of accountability due to a mental illness.
- Jury decision (verdict): decision made after taking the case into consideration.
- Schizophrenia: a mental illness in which an individual perceives reality abnormally.
 - Symptoms: delusions, hallucinations, disorganized thinking and speech, abnormal motor behavior or the lack of being able to function in a normal way, extreme mood changes, may be suicidal
- Stigma: a mark of dishonor or disgrace regarding a characteristic of an individual or a group of people.

In closing, this chapter consisted of an introduction to the overall topic of my study, the statement of the problem, the purpose statement, my research questions and hypotheses, as well as definitions of key terms necessary to understanding my study. In the following chapter, I will further discuss my theoretical perspective, review of literature, and the methodology used to conduct and complete this study.

Chapter 2:

Theoretical Perspective, Review of Literature, and Methodology

Theoretical Perspective

In the court system, the jury is a very prominent feature when deciding the sentencing of a defendant in both criminal and civil cases. The main role for the jury is to listen to the evidence given in court, establish which evidence may be factual and which evidence should be considered during their decision and then make inferences based on the evidence to form the basis of the sentencing the defendant shall receive. The main problem, however, is during the establishment of the evidence stage. In some cases, the defendant may be suffering with a mental illness, yet that may not be considered when the jury decides a verdict. Due to that, those suffering with a mental illness do not receive the treatment they need in order to help cope with their mental disorder. Of course, not every mental illness is given the same treatment, which could be a factor on why juries may take into consideration one mental illness compared to one that may not be perceived as severe as the other. That leads to the reason for this study; to compare different defendant with two different mental illnesses to each other as well as compare defendants with a mental illness to a defendant with no mental illness.

There is a significant amount of literature that has already been published regarding defendants suffering from a mental illness and how they are viewed in court, yet I am taking on a more in-depth approach. Most literature on this topic tend to focus on one defendant with one mental illness as well as use more common mental disorders. The common mental disorders being described in the study are usually anxiety which affects 18.1 percent and depression which affects 6.7 percent of the United States population every year according to the Anxiety and Depression Association of America. For this study, the approach that I took added a rarer mental disorder, schizophrenia, which affects only 1.1 percent of the United States population, and compared the disorder to depression as well as no mental illness. Having three defendants with three different mental illnesses gave a better understanding on how much juries take into consideration the type of mental illness the defendant is suffering from. The literature revealed that juries, more commonly, do not base their sentencing on the mental state of the defendant or do not believe that the mental illness had anything to do with the crime committed. In response to that, I took the opposing position and stating that jurors show more leniency in criminal sentencing with defendants with a more severe mental illness.

Review of Literature

As reported by the American Psychiatric Association, approximately 20 percent of prison inmates have a serious mental illness, and between 2.3 and 3.9 percent of inmates suffer with

schizophrenia or other severe mental illnesses. This left many to question on whether the inmates' mental illness is taken into consideration during the sentencing period and if so, are they given any treatment to help cope with these psychotic disorders. This is a problem in the sense that defendants are not being served the justice that they deserve given their mental state of mind. In this portion, I will discuss the themes of morality, insanity, and juror perceptions as it relates to sentencing of defendants and the leniency, if given, to those suffering with a mental illness.

Those suffering with mental illnesses or disorders can tend to view morality and ethics in a different spectrum than those who are sane as seen through Elaine Martin and Kenneth J. Weiss' article, *Knowing Moral and Legal Wrong in an Insanity Defense*. In the *State v. Winder* case of 2009, psychiatric experts concluded that Winder did not believe shooting the cab driver was wrong due to the reasoning of him trying to save himself from his delusions. He believed that being imprisoned would stop the voices and prevent them from killing himself; in order to go to prison, he had to commit a crime severe enough for that type of sentence (Martin & Weiss, 2010). Through further evaluation, Winder was a man who knew that his act was legally wrong, but not morally wrong in the sense that all he wanted was to preserve his life. Knowing this, one should have taken into consideration the sickness covering his ability to comprehend morality in a legal standpoint. The importance of this study was to illustrate the model charges on insanity and how there are specific measures that should be taken when dealing with a defendant who does not have the same moral spectrum than those who are sane. From this research, I used the emphasis of the *M'Naughten* rule as well as the *N.J. Stat. Ann. 2C:4-1* model charge on insanity. Already acknowledging the *M'Naughten* rule, one should know what the rule consists of regarding jury verdicts.

The *M'Naughten* rule is a common factor when dealing with defendants with mental illness. The rule was named after Daniel M'Naughten who was caught attempting to kill England's prime minister in 1843, but instead shot the prime minister's secretary. After evaluation of the defendant, experts concluded that M'Naughten was mentally insane and was found not guilty of his actions. Through the years, the *M'Naughten* rule is a test to determine whether the defendant, at the time the crime was committed, was sane and capable of knowing that the act committed was wrong. Experts have also limited the insanity defense to cognitive insanity which further emphasizes that the plea should only be taken into consideration if the defendant mental state had no way of differentiating right from wrong. As stated in the previous paragraph, for my study, the *M'Naughten* can be implemented by the jurors. The mock jurors had the ability to sentence the defendant as not guilty due to reason of insanity which will be under the *M'Naughten* rule. The significant take away from this piece is to review the different charges that can be taken place for defendant with a mental illness. Yet, the *M'Naughten* rule can be disregarded by individuals due to predetermined prejudice.

Another factor taken into deliberation is aversive racism as published by John F. Dovidio and Samuel L. Gaertner, *Aversive Racism*. Aversive racism can be appraised as having an

internal bias and or prejudice towards groups of individuals yet is taking place in our unconscious without any realization. It is a form of discrimination that is implicit making it difficult to understand as an individual (Dovidio & Gaertner, 2004). At times, without an individual acknowledging it, their actions are implicitly negative to another group of people which can be common when dealing with someone with a mental illness. It does not have to be in a court room, but aversive bias can also be seen in the outside world as most people would rather move away than walk next to someone who is seen talking to themselves or having mental problems out in the streets. This is extremely common, yet hard to evaluate as our thoughts are internal and not out in the open. From this research, I evaluated whether jurors are inclined towards aversive bias when perceiving defendants with mental illnesses compared to those without. The question of, “are jurors basing their sentencing on the mental illness?”, also arose and was observed through the follow up questions at the end of the study.

In “The twilight zone between scientific certainty and legal sufficiency: Should a jury determine the causation of schizophrenia?” by Robert L. Goldstein, the morality of jurors is being examined through a court case and how their sentences are being based off a false pretense. Goldstein accentuates the difference between the medical and legal concepts of what can cause schizophrenia and put this into effect through jury decision making (Goldstein, 1987). This goes hand in hand with aversive bias, as jurors’ sentencing are evaluated through their misleading perceptions on schizophrenia from the start of the trial. This is significant as Goldstein illustrates the flaws in the legal system when dealing with a defendant with a mental illness such as schizophrenia. I further emphasized his point being made that sentencing can be extremely unjust due to the false implications that individuals have on those suffering with a mental illness. Similar to morality, as seen through the literature, the definition of insanity and the insanity plea is just as difficult to pinpoint for everyone.

When having the ability to charge a defendant as not guilty due to reason of insanity, the severity of the crime committed should be noted as well as the culpability of the defendant. Sherri L. McGraw and Linda A. Foley highlight through their study, *Perceptions of Insanity Based on Occupation of Defendant and Seriousness of Crime*, that insanity is perceived differently due to individual definitions of the term. Through their own definitions, they hypothesized: (1) the less intelligent defendant is less responsible in their crime; (2) easier to perceive the defendant as insane when the crime is not as severe; (3) if the crime is more severe, it is more likely to perceive the defendant as responsible; (4) more likely to sentence the defendant to a prison when the crime is more serious; and (5) high belief in a just role will give more responsibility to the defendant (McGraw & Foley, 2000). McGraw and Foley use a different approach as they do not set a restriction on what should be considered as the set definition of insanity, which is a very difficult task to do, yet without it, leaves too much gray area for jurors when sentencing the defendant. This is significant as I do not agree with their findings which was that those who are mentally insane should be punished in the same manner as

other criminals. From this research, I contradicted their findings and hypothesis in hopes of gaining a different outcome.

As seen through previous studies, it is difficult to come up with one definition for insanity as there are many complexities that are too broad to limit into one solid definition. In *Definitions of Insanity in College Students*, John F. Greiger and Lawrence Weinstein illustrate seven different types of definitions for insanity based on different approaches: (1) moral model; (2) medical model; (3) statistical model; (4) sociological model; (5) psychometric model; (6) professional judgment model; and (7) legal model (Greiger & Weinstein, 2008). Through these seven different kinds of models, one can predict that, depending the level of intelligence in each field and profession of everyone, there will be varied sentences for each defendant that pleads insanity. There is not one umbrella definition that covers each model and that most psychologists can agree on. From this research, I used their legal model definition of insanity which defines insanity as an abnormal behavior and or way of thinking which can interfere with the lack of ability to understand right from wrong. This plays an important role in my study as I set a concrete definition of insanity for the jurors to have in mind when sentencing each of the three defendants, yet this is not the only factor that should be considered.

The severity of the mental disorder is also a prominent factor that should be taken under review when sentencing those with the insanity plea. Melissa LaVan, Helen LaVan, and William M. Marty Martin presented a study portraying the differences between criminal and civil cases dealing with schizophrenia. Criminal court cases take into consideration that the defendant is suffering with schizophrenia, whereas civil cases do not take their mental state into liability (LaVan, 2016). That being said, those in civil cases suffering with schizophrenia are not being granted the treatment that they should rightfully be allowed to have in order to help with their mental illness. They are being given a harsher sentence and are then stripped from the help that they need. M. LaVan, H. LaVan, and Martin further emphasize the defects revolving around the legal system when dealing with those suffering with a mental illness which is something I highlighted in my study. This puts into perspective the number of defendants in the United States that were given unjust sentences due to the lack of consideration for their mental health. This leads to my last theme: juror perceptions.

It is crucial to know background information on the defendant since perceptions of jurors may take certain aspects into consideration, for example, mental illness. In *Mock Juror Perceptions of Credibility and Culpability in an Autistic Defendant* by Katie Maras, Imogen Marshall, and Chloe Sands, participants were separated into two groups: one group knew that the defendant had autism spectrum disorder (ASD) while the other group did not. The group that knew the defendant had ASD were more lenient towards their sentencing of the defendant as they took the mental illness into consideration (Marshall & Sands, 2019). However, the second group that thought of the defendant as being mentally sane, viewed his autistic characteristics as being violent and hostile, traits that made him look more guilty to the jurors. There may not have been a split in jury decisions if both groups were given the same amount of information, but that

is what the researchers were interested in understanding. It is essential to grasp how jurors and legal authorities in the court system perceive mental ill individuals and whether they take into account what these individuals are suffering with. Maras, Marshall, and Sands' hypotheses correlate to mine as they predicted that adding a label to the defendant regarding their mental illness would result into jurors finding the defendant less credible of the act committed. Nonetheless, there are limitations that may occur.

One of the few problems, that can occur, however, is that when given the information of a defendant's mental illness, those who already have a pre-conditioned stigma or prejudice of mental ill individuals can result into a biased sentencing without any further thought of the case. Annik Mossiere and Evelyn M. Maeder conducted a study that portrayed defendants of different mental illness who have committed second-degree murder and are pleading insanity in front of jurors in Canada in order to observe if mental illness was taken into consideration. Their research involved examining the interplay between insanity pleas and mental illness to jury sentencing (Mossiere & Maeder, 2015). By the end of the study, there was a significance in the jury verdicts for those with a more severe type of mental illness which was schizophrenia, (schizophrenia was being compared to bipolar disorder, substance abuse, and depression). This correlates with my study as I compared schizophrenia to depression as well as compared schizophrenia to no mental illness. An important aspect to take into consideration from this study that I used in my research is the not criminally on account of mental disorder defense (NCRMD).

Nonetheless, an alternative factor to consider as seen through the previous literature is the controllability and severeness of the mental disorder of the defendant. Another study that was conducted using autism spectrum disorder was by Colleen M. Berryessa, Lauren C. Milner, Nanibaa' A. Garrison, and Mildren K. Cho titled *Impact of Psychiatric information on Potential Jurors in Evaluation high-functioning autism spectrum disorder (hfASD)*. In this study, the researchers concluded that most of the participants did not consider hfASD to be a severe mental disorder therefore sentencing was harsher than if the participants perceived hfASD to be less controllable (Berryessa, 2015). There can be an observable flaw in the way that legal systems are ran by reading this article, as beliefs and thoughts of mental illness can widely differ, leaving mental illness, such as hfASD, to be questioned whether it should even be considered mental illness at all. This is compelling to consider as individual perceptions play a giant role in sentencing and their thoughts of mental illness. For my research, since I have three cases, each with a defendant with a different mental state of mind, I took this into consideration as this can play a factor in analyzing each of the defendants' sentences given by the mock jurors.

Taking all the literature presented under further analysis, there are not many articles that take into consideration the severity of the mental illness of the defendant when dealing with a more violent crime. Out of all the papers that I have reviewed, only one, written by Annik Mossiere and Evelyn M. Maeder, speaks forth about comparing schizophrenia with other disorders in a murder case. The literature that I have reviewed are pointing a deficit in the area of research regarding schizophrenia compared to other mental illnesses in a legal standpoint. This

paper was published in 2015, which may not be too far into the past, but there is still research that is yet to be conducted to determine all factors of schizophrenia in legal cases. This paper is congruous with my hypothesis that jurors are more lenient when dealing with a defendant with schizophrenia.

In summary, I discussed the themes of morality, insanity, and juror perceptions as it relates to sentencing of defendants and the leniency, if given, to those suffering with a mental disorder. According to the American Psychiatric Association, mental illness in inmates is on the rise, yet, in my opinion, many do not take into consideration the suffering of these individuals and the lack of help given in the court systems. My study addresses the gaps in the literature, such as comparing schizophrenia to other mental disorders (depression) and comparing schizophrenia to a defendant with no mental disorder, in order to get a better understanding of jury sentencing and empathy.

Methodology

As recognized by the literature, there are breaks in the overall topic of mental illness in the legal system that have either not been addressed or have been addressed marginally. The problem here is not that defendants with mental illnesses should not be allowed in jails or prisons, but that the jury may not take the mental illness into consideration when it comes to sentencing, leaving the defendant at risk of having no treatment to help them with their mental disorder. However, that problem breaks off into other branches of problems that are noted in this study. For example, one branch that trails off from the main problem is that certain mental illnesses are not seen as severe as others. Colleen M. Berryessa, Lauren C. Milner, Nanibaa' A. Garrison, and Mildren K. Cho make a great example in their literature in analyzing how their jury did not view the mental disorder of high functioning autism spectrum disorder (hfASD) as a mental illness that should be considered a prime component in sentencing due to the aspect of "high functioning". Even though this autistic disorder may be considered as high functioning, it is still categorized as a mental disorder and have symptoms that the defendants may suffer from. According to the Bureau of Justice, approximately 24 percent of state prisoners, 21 percent of jail inmates, and 14 percent of federal prisoners suffered through some sort of mental illness prior to be sentenced, but they do not relate the information of the type of mental illness or whether it was taken into consideration during their time of the trial. The gap in the literature communicates this problem by having a lack of studies that compare different mental ill defendants who have committed the same crime and then analyzing what the jury decides for each defendant. There is an abundant amount of literature that focuses on one mental illness case in the legal system, yet it is important to address how and what makes one mental illness more severe and worth recognizing compared to another during the trial. This will primarily be based on both forensic and abnormal psychology. Hence forth, that is why, in my study, not only did I analyze the sentencing the jury gave to a defendant with schizophrenia, but also analyzed and compared schizophrenia to depression, schizophrenia to no mental illness, and depression to no mental illness.

The objective of the study is to address whether mitigating factors, such as mental illness, should play a role in jury verdicts using a quantitative approach. The overall goal is to analyze if mental illness holds a significant part in jury sentencing, and if so, compare the different types of mental illnesses to possibly observe whether one has more of an impact on the sentencing than the other. The following four questions will guide this quantitative study. Do jurors show more empathy towards defendants with a mental illness? Do jurors show more leniency in criminal sentencing towards a defendant with schizophrenia compared to a defendant with depression or no mental illness? Do jurors show more leniency towards a defendant with depression compared to a defendant with no mental illness? Lastly, how does the severity of a defendant's mental illness impact juror perceptions? The hypotheses implemented are as followed. First, I predict that jurors will show more leniency towards defendants with mental illness. Second, defendants with schizophrenia will have a more lenient sentencing compared to a defendant with depression or no mental illness. Third, defendants with depression will have a more lenient sentence compared to a defendant with no mental illness. Fourth, the severity of a defendant's mental illness will substantially impact juror perceptions.

In the previous section, I presented a summary of the problem and the reason for my study. I then continued to provide my purpose statement as well as followed up with my research questions that lead to my hypotheses. The methodology section is provided to present the how, when and where the data was collected to further emphasize the reason for choosing a quantitative approach for this study. Moving forward, I provided a description of my research design within the quantitative study approach that I utilized in my study. Following the research design, I gave detailed information on the specific research tools and methods used in the study to obtain and analyze my data. There are different categories to separate each area of information. The description includes information about the setting of the study, description of study sample, research design and procedures, data collection, data analysis, and delimitations and limitations of the study. Implemented in the analysis is also the triangulation and role of the researcher for this study. I conclude with a summary of the chapter and what to expect for the chapter that follows.

Setting of the Study

The study took place online through Qualtrics. The important note to consider with this study is that participants were asked to read three mock court cases in the beginning and then answer questions that deal with the cases. At the very end, each participant filled out their individual background information in order to record the population of participants. Qualtrics made the study more efficient and feasible as participants were able to do the study from their home and not be put at risk due to the ongoing pandemic of COVID-19. The system also made it easier to manage since individuals can take their time reading each court case and had the availability to go back to answer the follow-up questions from each mock court cases. If participants needed to go back or were called to do something in the middle of the study, their

answers were saved and recorded to ensure that nothing was deleted or timed-out before the study had been completed.

Description of Study Sample

In order to address the greater of the population, the study was sent out to the public making it available for anyone over eighteen years of age to complete. The reason for this being that California law states an individual needs to be at least eighteen years old in order to be a potential juror. There were three main methods on how I was able to gain access to these participants. The first was through social media platforms such as Instagram and snapchat. The link to the study on Qualtrics was sent individually to those that met the age requirement for the study. The link was also placed in a bigger platform for anyone to click on it yet were informed that they must be at least eighteen years of age to complete the study. The second method to gaining access of the participants were through individual emails. The link was sent along with a description on what the study consisted of and approximately how long it was to take. Emails were an easier way for participants to get a hold of the study and know exactly which one to take to be part of this study. The last method was through the psychology database at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF). In this database, psychology majors or students in lower-level psychology classes were able to see this study on their homepage. Most psychology professors teaching classes make it a requirement to complete a specific number of studies, giving an incentive to complete this study. This was also beneficial as the diversity of the participants competing the study increased. The sample consists mostly of those from their early twenties up to early sixties. There were also diverse ethnicities and races (Caucasian, Hispanic, African American, and Asian) which allows for a more profound analysis of the jury perceptions on criminal sentencing for each of the three mock court cases.

The perceptions of the participants informed the research study as I was able to analyze how potential jurors, of different ages and ethnicities, judged different defendants that have committed murder. Each participant was asked to read each court case regarding a defendant that either suffered through schizophrenia, depression, or did not suffer from any mental illness. From there, each participant was asked to sentence each defendant and whether they took into consideration the mental state of the defendant. This gives the study greater importance and meaning since this allows us to observe how jurors may think in actual court cases that deal with mental illness. In alignment with IRB requirements for ethical protection, I made sure to comply with the regulations and principles: 1) participants voluntarily consented to completing the study; 2) the voluntarily consent was informed consent; 3) protection of privacy was incorporated into the study; and 4) participants were given the ability to withdraw from the research if need be. Participants were also kept anonymous to protect their ethical values and to remain unbiased regarding the analysis of individual submissions. From the background information at the end of the study, participants were not asked to give their name or anything that could be used to verify their identity. The questions that were asked were gender, age, ethnicity, and household

information (income and number of people living in the same house). The last set of questions were beliefs and thoughts regarding certain subjects corresponding to the study.

Research Design/Procedures

The research design used to guide this study was a quantitative approach. I used multiple cases studies which are presented as mock court cases. Each mock court case holds a defendant with a different mental state of mind that is being analyzed and possibly considered by each participant when deciding a sentence for their crime committed. The quantitative method was the most beneficial approach for this study as it allowed for a larger pool of participants due to it being an analytical social study. This study is to better understand whether potential jurors will take into consideration the psychological illnesses of defendants when deciding a sentence. Utilizing the quantitative method, the study allowed for a more in-depth analysis of the set of questions asked for the participants to answer as well as an overall generalization of the results that answer the research questions. These answers fill in the area of deficit regarding research concerning schizophrenia compared to other mental illnesses in a legal standpoint and juror perceptions on mental illness in court.

The first line of order was securing participants for the study. In order to secure participants, this study was sent out through different methods of communication. The most efficient and quickest way was through direct emailing of the study link. The second way was through social media platforms in which many people are able see the link and click it to go straight to the study database, Qualtrics. The last method of securing participants was through the psychology database at California State University, Fullerton. In this database, psychology students or those taking a psychology course, are allowed access to different studies that they would wish to participate in. As soon as the study and the mock court cases were verified, the link of the study was sent out in order to have enough time to obtain a numerous amount of participants. In each one of these methods, the results were efficiently recorded.

The most crucial part of the study was coming up with mock court cases that emphasized different mental illnesses and mental state of minds for the defendants. Since the study compared a schizophrenic defendant to a depressed defendant, a schizophrenic defendant to a defendant with no mental illness, and a depressed defendant to a defendant with no mental illness, I made sure to have three different mock court cases acknowledging a defendant with a different mental state. However, to get more accurate results, each mock court case had the exact same crime that was committed, yet the defendant's background corresponds to the different mental illness. The crime committed in all three cases is a triple homicide, but the jury gets to read the background of the defendant as well as their psychological evaluation, which they may take into consideration during the decision making of the study. I made sure to separate each court case to where participants did not get the defendant's mental state confused with the other. Right after participants finish reading the closing arguments for the defense in each mock court case, participants are then asked to answer the juror verdict and sentence form for the specific defendant. They have the options to

choose not guilty, not guilty by reason of insanity, and guilty. If participants found the defendant not guilty by reason of insanity, they will then answer follow up questions on the reasoning behind their decision. If participants found the defendant guilty, they will then answer follow up questions on the reasoning behind their decision as well. This then led to the juror opinion form, the personal evaluation of the defendant, and lastly, the juror memory form. These question forms gave me a better understanding on how the participants perceived each defendant during the trial and whether they took into consideration the mental state of the defendants. The last set of questions at the very end of the entire study was the juror background information in which I collected the data from to observe the sample of the population that completed the study.

After obtaining the data, the data was then put into an Excel spreadsheet to make it more accessible and quicker to look at what participants answered regarding the different question forms. The first set of questions that were taken into consideration was the juror background information form. Participants were asked a set of questions in order to get a sense of who the participants were and their general background in order to be placed in a specific category during the analysis portion of the study. The questions that were asked were: number of people living in their household, combined household income, level of academic completion for the mother and father of the participant, gender, age, nationality, political beliefs, political party, and a pair of questions regarding how they view mental illness in the outside world. On the Excel spreadsheet, I divided the column into two parts; the first part being male participants and the second part, right below the first part, are the female participants. Below each subheading (Males or Females), I inputted the number of male participants for the first part and the number of female participants in the second part. This then made it easier to just go down the rows and input the information for each participant. The B column was for nationality; the C column was for age; the D column was the total number of people living in their household; the E column was their total household income; the F column was the level of education their father completed; the G column was the level of education their mother completed; the H column was the political beliefs which ranged from one to seven on a number scale, one being conservative whereas seven being liberal; and the last column, column I, was the political party the participant most associated with.

The next set of questions that needed to be collected before starting the analysis, were the juror opinion forms. The nineteen questions focused on the specific observations and opinions each participant had for the defendant of the case that they had just read. Each question was ranked on a number line by a scale of one to seven; seven being the more severe case of opinion for each answer. These were put into an Excel spreadsheet corresponding to the background information for each participant that was mentioned earlier. They followed the same guidelines as the background information format on the Excel spreadsheet, but numbers were inputted due to the number scale.

The last set of questions that needed to be inputted were the personal evaluation of each defendant from each participant. These questions were logged in to identify the defendant on multiple personality dimensions. These dealt with trustworthiness, likeableness, competence,

ethics, consideration, attractiveness, intelligence, sensitiveness, aggressiveness, and whether the participant believed the defendant had a mental illness. Similar to the juror opinion forms, these set of questions were also ranked on a number scale from one to nine. These answers were in their own category in the Excel spreadsheet, but they corresponded to the background information for each defendant.

From the spreadsheet, I was able to view how many participants were from one specific background and how their responses to the study may have been due to their background information.

After gathering all the data and inputting them into one spreadsheet to look at, I began to analyze what was on the Excel spreadsheet. I decided to analyze certain categories using bar graphs and the other categories using pie graphs to make it clearer and easier to read. The categories that were put into pie charts were the background information for each of the participants. There were different pie charts for age, nationality, household information, political beliefs, political parties, and the academic levels of the parents of each participant. I believed that the pie charts were better for this set of information as it was easier to compare the different groups by using percentages. On the other hand, I believed that bar graphs were easier to track the set of questions involving number lines: the juror opinion form and the personal evaluation form. The bar graphs made it simpler to view the patterns in the responses of each participant.

Subsequently, the data was then transferred over to the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). To better analyze and understand the data given, I used the tool of frequency distributions on SPSS. On “data view”, I inputted the data as it was on the Excel spreadsheet and then went inside “variable view” to categorize each variable that I will be analyzing for each participant. After each variable was inputted and marked, I analyzed the data using descriptive statistics in which frequency distributions fall under. “Descriptive statistics” is located at the top of the tool bar under “analyze”. I then created a frequency graph and made sure to click the button that allowed me not only to view my data in a frequency table, but also in a bar graph that displayed each variable. I was able to input a normal curve for each of my graph to analyze whether there was a positive skew or a negative skew for each frequency. The test that was used after observing the frequency distribution of each of the participants’ answers was the Chi Square test of Independence.

Data Collection

For this study, the main method of data collection was Qualtrics. The study consisted of three mock court cases that were similar to court cases that could be seen in an actual jury. This included the indictment, case summary, defendant background, defendant plea, summary case for prosecution, summary case for the defense, opening arguments for the defense, closing arguments for the defense, and the jury verdict and sentence form for each of the three mock court cases. Each individual participant was then asked to complete a juror opinion form, a personal evaluation of the defendant, as well as a juror memory form that dealt with the case description following each

of the three court cases. The juror background information was the last set of questions asked for each participant in order to collect the number of participants as well as the category that they were placed in regarding their age, gender, ethnicity, and household information. The overall number invited to participate in the study were 240 people.

Data Analysis

As previously stated, the management systems used to help in analyzing the data were Qualtrics, Excel spreadsheet, and SPSS. The study was first set up on Qualtrics in which participants were asked to read three separate mock court cases and then answer follow up questions at the end of the trial. The data collected from each participant was then placed into an Excel spreadsheet. Each column and row corresponded to a different variable that was taken into consideration when analyzing the study sample. Each individual variable corresponded to a different question that the participant had to answer in order to complete the study. The data that was inputted in the Excel spreadsheet was then inputted into SPSS to analyze the descriptive statistics of each frequency. The frequency distributions provided an organized set of numbers of individuals in each category on a scale of measurement. SPSS also allowed for a more detailed bar graph and pie chart to analyze what was more frequently occurring for each one of the variables. From there, the data was easier to analyze on the number of participants that viewed the defendants as guilty, not guilty, or not guilty by reason of insanity by using the Chi Square Test of Independence. The initial questions of the study were then put side by side to the findings in order to interpret the answers the data is displaying. Do jurors show more empathy towards defendants with a mental illness? Do jurors show more leniency in criminal sentencing towards a defendant with schizophrenia compared to a defendant with depression or no mental illness? Do jurors show more leniency towards a defendant with depression compared to a defendant with no mental illness? Lastly, how does the severity of a defendant's mental illness impact juror perceptions? From the data, I was able to start predicting what the answers to the questions are, but I still did not make any conclusions.

In order to ensure triangulation in this quantitative study, I not only collected my own data, but also took into consideration other information of data from other studies that were in the same criteria as mine. As seen through the literary review, there were a few published studies that corresponded to my predictions regarding jurors perceiving defendants with a mental illness. After collecting my data, I analyzed the similarities and differences between my data and data that was collected from other studies. Another way that I ensure triangulation was through meeting the IRB requirements for quantitative studies and following their principles of ethics.

Delimitations or Limitations of the Study

This study was innovative in analyzing potential juror perceptions on defendants with mental illnesses by using three mock court cases, each having a defendant with a different mental state (one suffering with schizophrenia, another suffering with depression, and one with no mental illness). Previous studies have a deficit in the area of research regarding schizophrenia compared

to other mental illnesses in a legal standpoint such as court trials. There are many studies that deal with schizophrenic defendants, but very few that analyze the differences amongst sentencing between a defendant with schizophrenia to a defendant with another mental illness or the difference in sentencing between a defendant with schizophrenia to a defendant with no mental illness.

However, there are also limitations to consider with this study. While the study was open to any age over the age of eighteen years old as well as any ethnicity, the sample did not cover a large part of the population. There were races and ages that were not observed in the study that would have allowed for a deeper analysis and a more diverse population across the United States. Additionally, data was collected over the course of a couple of months, which may not have allowed enough time to gain a larger study sample.

Conclusion

In this chapter, the theoretical perspective, a review of literature, and the methodology of the study was discussed. The focus of the study was to observe how potential jurors perceive defendants with mental illnesses during a trial. The jury plays a crucial role in sentencing for both criminal and civil cases which is why this study lets participants decide whether they think each defendant from each mock court case is guilty of the crime that they may have committed. In order to further emphasize the reason for the study, it was important to first acknowledge the problems in society that are discussed within the study. The main problem is that jurors may not take into consideration a defendant's mental illness during the trial and sentencing as seen through jury verdicts in previous cases. Not taking into consideration the mental state of a defendant leads to the follow up problem: lack of treatment, once admitted to a jail or prison, for the defendants that are mentally ill. This does not apply to all jurors, but from reading the literature, there are many deficits in this area of research. For example, having an inadequate number of studies that compare mental illnesses to other mental illnesses in the court system for similar crimes. The reasons for this study were to notice whether jurors showed empathy for defendants suffering with a mental illness, compare different defendants with two different mental illnesses to each other, as well as compare defendants with a mental illness to a defendant with no mental illness.

The next portion of this chapter focused on the literature review guiding the study. I took on a more in-depth approach when it came to mental illness in a legal standpoint as well as aversive bias that jurors may have had towards defendants with a mental illness. Reading the literature, I came across a pattern in most of the studies that stated that jurors did not show as much empathy as one predicted when it came to sentencing a defendant who was mentally ill. Jurors tended to focus on the severity of the mental illness which guided their decision. Due to this, I took on the opposing view from other studies and predicted that jurors will show more leniency towards defendants suffering with a mental illness. In the literature review, I discussed common themes found in the literature such as morality, insanity, and juror perception on

mentally ill defendants. This study addressed the gaps in the literature by comparing different mental disorders to better understand jury verdicts and sentencing.

Ultimately, a good portion of this chapter concentrated on the methodology of the study. The methodology section is provided to present the how, when and where the data was collected to further emphasize the reason for choosing a quantitative approach for this study. Using a quantitative approach allowed me to evaluate jury behaviors from a sample of participants and make a generalized prediction regarding the larger population. My goal was to analyze if mental illness holds a significant role in jury sentencing. If mental illness did hold a significant amount in jury sentencing, I compared different types of mental illnesses to view whether one had a larger impact over the other. In order to better understand my study and how the quantitative approach was applied, I provided a description of my research design within the quantitative study approach that I utilized in my study.

The sub-categories following the methodology portion discussed the essential steps taken in this study. The first sub-category to be explained was the setting of the study. The study took place in Qualtrics as participants were asked to read three mock court cases and the answer follow up questions pertaining to each case. The second sub-category was the description of the study sample. Participants were over the age of eighteen and there was a diverse group of participants (Caucasian, Hispanic, African American, and Asian). The perceptions of the participants informed the research study as I was able to analyze how potential jurors, of different ages and ethnicities, judged different defendants that have committed murder. Next was the research design/procedure in which I reviewed the steps I took to complete the study, starting from the creation of the three mock court cases and ending off on how I analyzed the data. The research design/procedure led up to how I collected the data in order to begin my analysis. I used Qualtrics, as stated from the setting of the study, and collected the data and answers given by the participants from the following forms: the juror opinion form, the personal evaluation form of each of the three defendants, the juror memory form, and the juror background information form. Using the data recorded from these four forms, I analyzed the data using Excel spreadsheets and the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). I also explained how I ensured triangulation through my analysis. The last sub-category for the methodology section was the delimitations or limitations of the study. Here I considered limitations that were out of my control which could have interfered with my results.

In closing, this chapter explained my approach to my study and how I collected my data using a quantitative approach. In the following chapter, I will further discuss my results from the study and how they fit in with my hypotheses.

Chapter 3

Results

As stated previously, there were four questions revolving around this study:

(1) Do jurors show more empathy towards defendants with a mental illness? (2) Do jurors show more leniency in criminal sentencing towards a defendant with schizophrenia compared to a defendant with depression or a defendant with no mental illness? (3) Do jurors show more leniency towards a defendant with depression compared to a defendant with no mental illness? Lastly, (4) How does the severity of a defendants' mental illness impact juror perceptions? Reviewing the data from a sample of 80 participants, there was a positive correlation between the severity of the mental illness and the criminal sentencing given by the potential jurors. All four hypotheses, as follow, were accepted regarding this study:

- Jurors showed more leniency towards defendants with a mental illness.
- Defendants with schizophrenia were given a more lenient sentencing compared to a defendant with depression or a defendant with no mental illness.
- Defendants with depression were given a more lenient sentence compared to a defendant with no mental illness.
- The severity of a defendants' mental illness did substantially impact the jurors' perceptions.

This chapter will provide a concise summary of the results, including gender, age, nationality, political beliefs, and the number of responses for each case.

Demographics

Starting with gender, females outnumber males (41 females, 34 males, and 1 prefer not to say). 54% females, 45% males, 0.01% prefer not to say, and 0% non-binary.

Secondly, for this study, the minimum age requirement was 18 years old due to 18 being the earliest age for a person to participate in jury duty. With some participants not inputting their age in the demographics section of the study, there was still a wide range of participants' ages.

Next, in order to have a wide range of variety with nationality, this study was extended to all races willing to participate. All 80 participants inputted their nationality allowing a more detailed presentation of the participants' demographics. For this study, 49% of participants were Hispanic; 19% of participants were African American; 18% of participants were Asian; 14% of participants were Caucasian; 0.01% were other; and 0% were Native American.

Lastly, political beliefs were important to this study as it allowed researchers to observe more liberal participants and how they sentenced each of the defendants compared to how more conservative participants sentenced each of the three defendants. Not all participants inputted their political beliefs, but 78 out of the 80 participants did. 71% of participants were democrat; 19% of participants were republican; 0.1% of participants were independent; and 0.03% were other.

Case Studies

For this study, participants were given one of each of the following case studies: a defendant with schizophrenia, a defendant with depression, or a defendant with no mental illness. Due to the number of participants not being evenly divided by three, the case study with schizophrenia had 5 more participants than the case study with a defendant with depression and the case study with a defendant with no mental illness. The number of participants that were given the mock court case with a schizophrenic defendant was 30, the number of participants that were given the mock court case with a defendant with depression was 25, and the mock court case with the defendant with no mental illness had 25 participants as well.

*Diagnos * Verdict Crosstabulation*

Count

		Verdict			Total
		NGBRI	Guilty	Not Guilty	
Diagnos	schizophrenia	23	7	0	30
	Depression	2	23	0	25
	No diagnosis	1	23	1	25
Total		26	53	1	80

Having chosen a verdict for the defendant, mock-jurors were then asked to choose a sentence that corresponds to their verdict; they were given three choices for each verdict. If the mock-juror chose “Not Guilty due to Reason of Insanity”, the options were: (1) Released under the supervision of psychiatrist Sally Jenkins; (2) Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff; or (3) Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff, whereby the defendant will serve 20 years for the murders. If the mock-juror chose “Guilty”, the options were: (1) Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 20 years and time for good behavior; (2) Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 30 years and time for good behavior; or (3) Life in prison without the possibility of parole.

*Diagnos * Sentence Crosstabulation*

Count

		Sentence					
		Guilty and 20 years	Guilty and 30 years	Guilty life in prison	NGBRI Release after treatment	NGBRI Treatment then serve 20 years	Total
Diagnos	schizophrenia	2	3	2	10	13	30
	Depression	3	9	11	1	1	25
	No diagnosis	0	1	22	1	0	24
Total		5	13	35	12	14	79

Schizophrenia

The case of the defendant with schizophrenia was the most looked at amongst the 80 participants in this study as 30 participants read and answered the questions for this specific mental illness case. As seen from the table above, twenty-three out of thirty mock-jurors chose the verdict of “Not Guilty due to Reason of Insanity” and only seven mock-jurors saw the defendant as “Guilty”; no one chose the verdict of “Innocent”.

For many of the cases, those who chose “Not Guilty due to Reason of Insanity” also chose the sentence “Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff, whereby the defendant will serve 20 years for the murders”. The next most chosen sentence for this verdict was “Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff”. No one chose the sentence “Released under the supervision of psychiatrist Sally Jenkins”.

On the other hand, there were seven participants that did choose the verdict of “Guilty”. The most common sentence for this verdict was “Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 30 years and time for good behavior”. The last two sentences had an equal number of participants choosing either one of them.

Depression

The following case also deals with a mental illness (depression), but it did not receive the same results as the case dealing with a schizophrenia defendant. Opposite from the schizophrenia case, twenty-three out of twenty-five mock-jurors chose the verdict of “Guilty” despite the defendant having another form of mental illness; only two mock-jurors chose the verdict of “Not Guilty due to Reason of Insanity”.

Out of the twenty-three people that chose “Guilty” for the defendant, there was an equal number of participants that chose either “Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 30 years and time for good behavior” and “Life in prison without the possibility of parole”. That only leaves three people that chose “Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 20 years and time for good behavior”.

With twenty-three participants choosing “Guilty” as their verdict, only two participants chose “Not Guilty due to Reason of Insanity”. There were two options, one by each participant, “Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff”, and the other was, “Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff, whereby the defendant will serve 20 years for the murders”.

No Mental Illness

The last case that participants had a chance of viewing was the case where the defendant committed the exact same crime, however, the defendant had no mental illness. Twenty-three out of the twenty-five participants chose “Guilty”, one participant chose “Not Guilty due to Reason of Insanity”, and one participant even chose “Innocent” as their verdict.

Even though the same number of participants chose “Guilty” for the defendant with no mental illness as the defendant with depression, there was a difference in the type of sentence that the defendant with no mental illness received. Twenty-two participants out of the twenty-three chose the sentence “Life in prison without the possibility of parole” and only one participant chose “Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 30 years and time for good behavior”.

The other two participants chose a less harsh verdict for this defendant. As stated previously, one participant chose “Not Guilty due to Reason of Insanity” and chose the sentence “Placed in the Valley View Farms secured mental hospital until recommendation of release by psychiatric staff”; whereas the other participant chose the verdict of “Innocent”.

Statistical Reasoning

Viewing all three mock-court cases as well as the verdicts and sentences given by each participant for their specific case, there is an ongoing pattern that follows the hypotheses made for this study. Using a Chi-Square Test of Independence test, this study compared the leniency of each sentencing for each of the three specific mock-court cases. The study observed the relationship between the diagnosis of the defendant with the verdict that was given as well as comparing the diagnosis of the defendant and the sentence that was given.

H₀ : There is no relationship between a defendant’s diagnosis to the type of verdict given.

H₁ : There is a significant relationship between a defendant’s diagnosis to the type of verdict given.

H₀ : There is no relationship between a defendant’s diagnosis to the type of sentence given.

H₁ : There is a significant relationship between a defendant’s diagnosis to the type of sentence given.

Diagnosis*Verdict Table

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	44.416 ^a	4	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	47.606	4	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	34.599	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	80		

^a. 3 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .31.

A Chi-Square Test of Independence was performed to examine the relationship between the diagnosis of the defendant and the verdict given to the defendant. The relationship between these two variables was significant, $X^2(4, N = 80) = 44.42, p < 0.001$, rejecting the null hypothesis. The more severe the diagnosis, such as schizophrenia being compared to depression, mattered to jurors as they gave the defendant with more severity a more lenient verdict.

Diagnosis*Sentence Table

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	61.801 ^a	8	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	67.400	8	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.079	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	79		

^a. 11 cells (73.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.52.

Similarly, a Chi-Square Test of Independence was performed to examine the relationship between the diagnosis of the defendant and the sentence given to the defendant. The relationship between these two variables was significant, $X^2(8, N = 79) = 61.8, p < 0.001$, once again, rejecting the null hypothesis. With a more severe diagnosis, jurors gave the defendants a much lesser sentence compared to a diagnosis that they believed did not matter to crime or no diagnosis of a mental illness whatsoever.

Comparing all three mock-court cases once again after utilizing the Chi Square Test of Independence test, we can conclude that, on average, schizophrenic defendants received a more lenient sentencing compared to both the defendant with depression and the defendant with no mental illness. We can also conclude that, on average, defendants with depression received a more lenient sentencing than the defendants with no mental illness, despite one participant choosing the verdict of “Innocent” for the defendant with no mental illness. Overall, defendants with a mental illness will receive a lesser sentence and will receive more leniency from jury members. On the same hand, the more severe the mental illness, such as schizophrenia, also plays a crucial role in the jury’s perceptions when deciding the verdict; therefore, the severity of a defendants’ mental illness did substantially impact the jurors’ perceptions.

The following chapter will go more into detail about the results as well as what should be interpreted through these findings. Implications and recommendations will also extend the interpretations of these findings for steps for actions in terms of implications for practice, theory, and future research.

Chapter 4

Interpretations/Conclusions

Summary of Findings

The present study found that defendants suffering from a mental illness were given a more lenient and lesser sentence compared to defendants with no history of mental illness. Specifically, mock juror participants who were given the mock court case with the defendant suffering from schizophrenia showed more empathy and were also more likely to suggest a “Not Guilty due to Reason of Insanity” verdict and were more lenient in their choosing of sentencing compared to mock juror participants who were given the mock court case with the defendant suffering from depression and the defendant with no mental illness.

Research Question Interpretation #1

The prime question in this study is: do jurors show more empathy towards defendants with a mental illness? My hypothesis was that jurors do in fact show more empathy towards defendants with a mental illness which is demonstrated in this study. Mock juror participants chose the verdict of “Not Guilty due to Reason by Insanity” for the defendants with mental illness more often compared to the defendant with no mental illness. Seventy-seven percent of participants that were in the schizophrenia court cases and eight percent of participants in the depression court case chose “Not Guilty due to Reason by Insanity” compared to only four percent of participants in the no mental illness court case; an eighty-one percent difference. We can interpret that mental illness is taken into consideration during jury verdicts and sentencing. Defendants with a mental illness will receive a lesser sentence and more leniency from jury members. This is consistent with previous research in which compassion is a symbolic factor in verdicts and sentencing by jurors (Maras et. al. 2018; Berryessa et .al. 2015; LaVan et. al. 2016).

Research Question Interpretation #2

Further undergoing the study, the next question that is evaluated is: do jurors show more leniency towards a defendant with depression compared to a defendant with no mental illness. The findings emphasize my hypothesis that yes, jurors do show more leniency towards a defendant with depression compared to a defendant with no mental illness. This was demonstrated through assessing the sentence that was given to each defendant when the defendant was found guilty. Even though the defendant with depression was found guilty, they were given a lesser sentence compared to the defendant with no mental illness. Twenty-two mock juror participants that found the defendant with no mental illness guilty gave the harsher sentence of “life in prison without the possibility of parole” compared to only ten mock juror participants that found the defendant with depression guilty: a forty-four percent difference. We conclude that, on average, there is a significant relationship between the verdicts for the defendant with depression and the verdicts for the defendants with no mental illness, therefore

rejecting the null hypothesis; $X^2(8, N = 79) = 61.8, p < 0.001$. In this case, the defendant with depression was given a more lenient sentence than the defendant with no mental illness.

Research Question Interpretation #3

The last two questions coincide together and are the most important questions that brought upon a more detailed aspect of this study: do jurors show more leniency in criminal sentencing towards a defendant with schizophrenia compared to a defendant with depression or no mental illness and how does the severity of a defendant's mental illness impact juror perceptions? Findings indicate that my hypotheses are correct; jurors do show more leniency in criminal sentencing towards defendants with schizophrenia which indicates that the severity of the mental illness does impact juror perceptions. Only seven mock jurors found the defendant with schizophrenia guilty compared to twenty-three mock jurors in the case with the defendant with depression and twenty-three of the mock jurors in the case with the defendant with no mental illness: a sixty-nine percent difference in each case comparing schizophrenia to others. This is consistent with previous research in which schizophrenia, seen as a more severe mental illness, is observed compared to other mental illnesses such as depression (Mossiere & Maeder, 2015; Berryessa et. al. 2015).

Strength and Limitations

There are multiple strengths in this study. First, randomization of each court case eliminates any form of biases that may occur if the experiment were not randomly assigned. Secondly, each mock court case had the same information with the only difference being the types of mental illness and whether the defendant has a mental illness. This ensured that each participant was given the same case with the same crime, so the severity of the crime did not waiver. Third, each mock court case gave clear instructions regarding how to answer the "Juror Verdict and Sentence form" and the "Juror Opinion form" which decreased the uncertainty and doubt participants may have had if not given proper instructions. Lastly, analysis and statistics were conducted and reviewed to ensure reliability and validity in each evaluation of the jury verdict and sentencing portion of the study.

Limitations are also acknowledged for this study. First, there were only eighty participants in this sample, which could be seen as too few representations of the overall population. Nevertheless, the sample still indicates that there is significant value in considering the mental illnesses of defendants regarding jury sentencing and verdicts. This could indicate that the significance would increase with an increase in participants. Secondly, there was not an even number of participants for each court case; the schizophrenia case had thirty participants whereas the depression and no mental illness case only had twenty-five participants. However, the schizophrenia case had a larger impact on juror perceptions than the depression and the no mental illness case, having the same number of participants in each court case would have not made a difference in the current findings.

Implications

The current findings that the act of providing the mental illness of defendants impacted mock juror perceptions regarding verdicts and sentencing, provides a significant example of the influence a diagnosis can have on perceptions of guilt. The present findings indicate that providing information on the defendant's mental illness in the court case allows a reduction of harsher sentencing towards individuals with mental illness. It is important to declare that the mental illness label should be included in order to have reasonable and justifiable adjustments to sentencing in order to establish a fair and unbiased trial.

Implications for Theory

Current theoretical frameworks indicate that mental illness is not always taken into consideration during the trial (Mossiere & Maeder, 2015); however, the act of providing analysis and description of mental illness is never declared. Connecting to previous literature, there is an ongoing belief that adding the mental illness, that a defendant may have, would cause jurors as well as judges to think that anyone can use mental illness as a "get out of jail free card" (Maras et. al. 2018). Nonetheless, knowledge of the defendant's mental illness can indicate whether they are sentenced to a psychiatric hospital in which they will undergo treatment that they need, or, be sentenced directly to a prison where they will receive no help for their psychological problems. In the present study, both mental illnesses, schizophrenia, and depression, are clearly stated and even given a description of the symptoms and types of episodes that each defendant underwent in the case study. The provision itself of adding a segment in the case study that implicates the defendant's state of mind is crucial and can alter how future jury members perceive both defendants suffering from mental illness and defendants with no mental illness.

Implications for Future Research

The current study only examined jurors' perceptions towards male defendants which highlights the need to further future research by replicating the study, but with female defendants. Future research should explore if the sex of the defendant, as well as the mental illness, of the defendants have a significant effect on juror perceptions. Is a female defendant suffering from a mental illness given a more lenient sentence compared to a male defendant suffering from a mental illness?

Recommendations

The current study allows us to review the results and findings from a more global perspective. In light of what the findings highlight and what previous studies have acknowledged, three recommendations are in order.

The first recommendation is that court cases should include the mental illness of the defendants as well as a summary and symptoms of the mental illness for jury members. In rare cases, mentally ill defendants are not seen fit to be on trial, meaning that many individuals suffering through psychological problems must undergo the same trial as individuals with no mental illness and receive the same sentence. Inputting a segment in the background information portion specifically on treatments, therapies, medications, and or illness that a defendant may have would give deeper knowledge to the jurors on whom they are judging and sentencing. As

seen in the present study, knowledge of the defendant's mental illness substantially impacted the jury's verdicts and sentencing.

The second recommendation is to begin having scheduled monthly psychological evaluations of inmates. This could include checking for mental illness or even just have group therapy sessions given by therapists or counselors willing to work in the court system. Evaluations and therapy sessions would allow officials working in the court system to observe whether specific inmates should be either sent to a mental institution or if they should be receiving medication for something that inmates could not control. The only flaw to this would be the cost and time necessary for these monthly evaluations. However, scheduling therapy sessions as groups would be less costly and would be easier to manage and begin straight away in a more organized and considerate manner.

The last recommendation is to enhance the knowledge of mental illnesses through a course requirement that could be input into the high school senior curriculum. There are two reasons why it would be more beneficial to be in the high school senior curriculum than any other. The first reason is that high school is still a mandated requirement for those up to the age of eighteen, meaning that they will have to take this course in order to graduate from high school. Any younger than seniors in high school would soon forget once they reach the age of eighteen and any older would mean that students would have to be mandated to enroll in a college in order to take the course. The second reason that it would be more beneficial to be in the senior curriculum is that high school seniors are roughly around the age of seventeen and eighteen which is the same age (eighteen) that individuals can begin to be chosen to be jury members. Undergoing this course requirement of abnormal psychology would provide the future and potential jurors more understanding of the defendant's mental illness, leaving little room for uncertainty and doubt regarding the mental illness in question as well as sentencing.

Conclusion

The present study focused on examining whether mental illness is considered in court cases and, if so, is the severity of the mental illness is also an important factor. Findings suggest that the defendant's mental illness can influence jury judgments and the severity of the mental illness has an even more profound effect. With the act of providing the mental illness label and section in the mock court case, such as schizophrenia and depression, and information of past therapy for defendants, defendants suffering from a mental illness were predominantly given a more lenient and lesser sentence. This has more important implications not only for psychological purposes, but also for courts and forensic purposes where the disclosure of mental illness on an individual may impact jurors' perceptions towards these defendants. Existing literature demonstrates opposing sides on whether there is a profound effect in considering mental illness in court cases, but the present findings add to the existing studies that suggest that mental illness is a prominent factor and should be considered in court cases. These findings hold significant implications and should be taken into consideration in both the abnormal and forensic psychology fields. With these findings being acknowledged, we could reduce the number of

mentally ill individuals in jails and prisons and, instead, send them to psychiatric hospitals in which they will receive the help and medication necessary.

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Format Requirements

The APA format is appropriate for my study.